

EUROPEAN ARREST WARRANT AND CONSTITUTIONAL GUARANTEES FOR ITS EFFECTIVENESS: STATE OF AFFAIRS IN NORTH MACEDONIA

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Injustice anywhere is a threat to justice everywhere

– Marthin Luther King

J.R.

Abstract

North Macedonia has been an EU candidate country since 2004. Although the accession negotiations have not yet begun, the country has already undertaken reforms comparable to those implemented by other states prior to accession. This fact, as well as the reality that EU law is a “moving target” i.e. constantly evolving, leads to the conclusion that North Macedonia must prepare for every issue that will inevitably arise during negotiations.

This paper briefly explores the *European Arrest Warrant* (hereinafter ‘EAW’) and its key elements, providing a comparative overview of *constitutional provisions* in several Eastern European EU member states that *ensure the effectiveness* of the EAW. It concludes with an examination of the position of the Constitution of North Macedonia regarding the extradition of domestic nationals.

The main conclusion of this study is that the Macedonian constitutional provision in Amendment XXXII could ensure enforcement of the EAW through interpretation. However, to avoid practical difficulties, consideration should be given to amending the text in a manner that explicitly refers to extradition to EU member states. Such an amendment would depend on the stage of negotiations and the readiness of Macedonian legal practitioners to embrace EU law.

Keywords: European Arrest Warrant, constitutional provisions, Eastern European EU member states, effectiveness, Constitution of North Macedonia

INTRODUCTION

North Macedonia’s path to European Union accession has proven to be long and complex. Shaped by both external and internal factors, the enlargement process for this small country remains on hold. Although candidate status was granted in 2004, and screening sessions for all six clusters were completed in December 2023, negotiations have yet to begin. Nevertheless, over the past two decades, numerous reforms and significant changes have been implemented. It is important to emphasize that many of these reforms were introduced in other countries during their negotiation processes for EU accession.

Therefore, it is reasonable to expect that once negotiations commence and clusters are opened, North Macedonia will achieve progress in certain areas at a faster pace than usually anticipated. Preparation for the next steps is essential.

One issue that requires particular attention is the European Arrest Warrant (EAW), a simplified cross-border judicial surrender procedure designed for prosecution or the

execution of custodial sentences or detention orders (European Commission, 2025). The constitutional dilemma arises from the fact that national constitutions typically prohibit the extradition of domestic nationals to other countries, or allow it only under strict conditions. In practice, this makes extradition an exceptional, lengthy, and demanding procedure.

The European Union is unique in its nature, and the EAW is a distinctive instrument of judicial cooperation. Advocate General Dámaso Ruiz-Jarabo Colomer succinctly described the EAW as follows: “The Framework Decision [...] abolished extradition and replaced it with a system of surrender between judicial authorities, based on mutual recognition and the free movement of judicial decisions. It results from a high level of confidence between member states. For the reasons stated, reciprocity and double criminality are presumed for certain offences – namely the most serious ones – and the grounds for refusing assistance are restricted, while there is no scope at all for political discretion.” (Sarmiento, 2008).

EUROPEAN ARREST WARRANT

The path toward extradition of domestic nationals within the European Union was opened with the Conclusions of the European Council in Tampere in 1999. Under the pressure of the events of 11 September 2001, and largely due to the initiative of the United Kingdom (Fennely, 2007), the Council Framework Decision on the European Arrest Warrant (Council of the EU, 2002) was adopted in 2002 (hereinafter: “Framework Decision”). It entered into force in 2004 and has since proven to be a successful instrument of legal assistance among EU member states.

The EAW replaced the lengthy extradition procedures previously in practice among member states. It simplified and accelerated the surrender of individuals suspected or convicted of serious crimes in EU member states. Among other objectives, the EAW aims “to remove the complexity and potential for delay inherent in the [...] extradition procedures, [...] and also, establish] a system of free movement of judicial decisions in criminal matters.” (Council of the EU, 2002, point 5 of introductory part).

According to the Framework Decision, the EAW is defined as “a judicial decision issued by a Member State with a view to the arrest and surrender by another Member State of a requested person, for the purposes of conducting a criminal prosecution or executing a custodial sentence or detention order.” (Council of the EU, 2002, Article 1). An EAW may be issued for two categories of acts:

- 1) acts punishable under the law of the issuing Member State by a custodial sentence or detention order for a maximum period of at least 12 months, or, where a sentence has already been passed or a detention order made, for sentences of at least four months, and
- 2) crimes listed in Article 2 Paragraph 2 of the Framework Decision, including terrorism, trafficking in human beings, corruption, laundering of proceeds of crime etc.¹¹

¹¹Those listed crimes are the following: participation in a criminal organisation, terrorism, trafficking in human beings, sexual exploitation of children and child pornography, illicit trafficking in narcotic drugs and psychotropic substances, illicit trafficking in weapons, munitions and explosives, corruption, fraud (including that affecting the financial interests of the European Communities within the meaning of the Convention of 26 July 1995 on the protection of the European Communities’ financial interests), laundering of the proceeds of crime, counterfeiting currency (including the euro), computer-related crime, environmental crime (including illicit trafficking in endangered animal species and plant species/varieties), facilitation of unauthorised entry and residence, murder, grievous

For the first category of crimes, double criminality must be verified. However, for the second category – given their seriousness and consequences – double criminality is presumed.

Article 6 of the Framework Decision stipulates that both the issuing and executing authorities must be judicial authorities designated by the law of the respective state. This provision excludes political interference in extradition matters and allows each member state to determine its competent judicial authority. The Framework Decision also sets out grounds for non-execution of the EAW, guarantees required in certain cases and time limits for execution.

The EAW was introduced as a response to the negative side effects of the free movement of workers, goods, services and capital, as well as the rise of serious international crime accompanying European integration. Nevertheless, the EAW sparked considerable debate due to the need to balance effective prosecution of crime with the obligation to respect principles of fairness and due process (Fennely, 2007).

The divergence of the EAW from classical extradition instruments is evident not only in its rules and procedures but also in its terminology – using with the word “surrender” instead of “extradite” a person. Importantly, academic commentary has emphasized that prohibitions on extradition of domestic nationals in legal acts, absent constitutional guarantees, do not prevent extradition under the EAW. Similarly, the constitutional provisions that forbid expulsion or deportation of domestic nationals, but do not explicitly mention extradition, can be interpreted as not preventing the surrender of nationals pursuant to the EAW (Deen-Racsmay, 2007).

The EAW has proven to be a useful instrument in judicial cooperation (European Commission, 2005). Examples of its successful application include:

- a terrorist involved in the Paris attacks caught in Belgium,
- an attacker of the Brussels Jewish Museum arrested in France,
- a failed London bomber apprehended in Italy,
- a German serial killer tracked down in Spain,
- a suspected drug smuggler from Malta surrendered by the UK,
- a gang of armed robbers sought by Italy, whose members were arrested in six different EU countries.

EU law is a “moving target” and is constantly evolving. Substantial case law has been developed (Agency for Fundamental Rights, 2025), positions have been taken and legislation has been upgraded. In February 2009, the Framework Decision was amended by the Council Framework Decision concerning trials *in absentia*, inserting a clear and common ground for non-execution of decisions rendered in the absence of the person concerned at trial (Council

bodily injury, illicit trade in human organs and tissue, kidnapping, illegal restraint and hostage-taking, racism and xenophobia, organised or armed robbery, illicit trafficking in cultural goods (including antiques and works of art), swindling, racketeering and extortion, counterfeiting and piracy of products, forgery of administrative documents and trafficking therein, forgery of means of payment, illicit trafficking in hormonal substances and other growth promoters, illicit trafficking in nuclear or radioactive materials, trafficking in stolen vehicles, rape, arson, crimes within the jurisdiction of the International Criminal Court, unlawful seizure of aircraft or ships, sabotage.

of the EU, 2009). Furthermore, the procedural rights of persons arrested on the basis of a European Arrest Warrant have been strengthened by six directives:

- the right to interpretation and translation(European Parliament and Council of the EU, 2010);
- the right to information(European Parliament and Council of the EU, 2012);
- the right of access to a lawyer (European Parliament and Council of the EU, 2013);
- strengthening certain aspects of the presumption of innocence and the right to be present at trial (European Parliament and Council of the EU, 2016);
- procedural safeguards for children (European Parliament and Council of the EU, May 2016)
- legal aid (European Parliament and Council of the EU, 2017).

Official statistics show that in 2022, judicial authorities of the 27 Member States issued a total of 13,335 EAWs. This represents a decrease compared to previous years, with 14,789 EAWs issued in 2021 and 15,938 in 2020.From the day of arrest, the surrender procedure took an average of 20.48 days when the requested person consented, and 57.29 days when the person did not consent.

The most commonly identified categories of offences in 2022 were:

- theft and criminal damage (1,963 EAWs),
- drug offences (1,711 EAWs)
- fraud and corruption (1,254 EAWs).

In 2022, 7,346 requested persons were arrested, compared to 7,262 arrests in 2021 and 6.152 arrests in 2020. The highest numbers of arrests in 2022 were recorded in Germany (1,667), Spain (947), the Netherlands (931) and Romania (596) (European Commission, 2025, p. 6, 8 and 13).

CONSTITUTIONAL SOLUTIONS FOR ENSURING EFFECTIVENESS OF THE EUROPEAN ARREST WARRANT

The EAW is an instrument that raises constitutional questions and dilemmas, since most countries generally prohibit the extradition of their own nationals. The manner of overcoming these issues differs among EU member states, but the most important consideration is to ensure the effective implementation of the arrest warrant.

This question was particularly relevant for Eastern European countries during their accession processes. In **Slovenia**, constitutional amendments in 2003 introduced a provision allowing extradition of domestic national if the obligation stems from an agreement by which “Slovenia has transferred the exercise of sovereign rights to international organization.”¹² Thus, Slovenia linked extradition exclusively to EU member states, since accession treaties provide for the transfer of sovereign rights to the European Union – a unique feature of this organization.

Although the principles of supremacy and direct effect of EU law bind member states to secure extradition of domestic nationals, in Slovenia the application of EU law conflicted with the previous constitutional provision of Article 47, which prohibited

¹² Article 47 of the Slovenian Constitution provides that: “No citizen of Slovenia may be extradited or surrendered unless such obligation to extradite or surrender arises from a treaty by which, in accordance with the provisions of the first paragraph of Article 3a, Slovenia has transferred the exercise of part of its sovereign rights to an international organization”.

extradition of nationals to foreign countries. Hence, the constitutional amendment ensured effective application of the EAW, while limiting extradition strictly to the EU.

The Constitution of **Latvia** (Article 98) prescribes an exception to the prohibition of extradition of nationals to foreign countries in cases provided for in international agreements, provided that extradition does not violate the basic human rights recognized in the Constitution.¹³ Similarly, Lithuania (Article 13) allows exception if prescribed in an international agreement.¹⁴ Through interpretation, the obligation to respect the EAW – stemming from accession agreements – means that the constitutions of Latvia and Lithuania do not pose an obstacle to effective judicial cooperation under the EAW.

Amendments to the **Romanian** Constitution in 2003 introduces an exception to the general prohibition of extradition of nationals.¹⁵ Article 19 allows extradition on the basis of international agreement, pursuant to law and on a mutual basis. Thus, through interpretation of “international agreement” as including accession agreements, Romania has ensured respect for the EAW.

The Constitution of **Bulgaria** provides an exception to the prohibition of extradition of nationals to other countries or international courts when established by international agreement.¹⁶ This provision served as the legal basis for compliance with the EAW. However, in 2004 the Bulgarian Constitutional Court went further, holding that surrender of a Bulgarian national to an EU member state does not constitute surrender to a “foreign state”, since Bulgarian nationals are also EU nationals (Constitutional Court of Bulgaria, 2004).

In Croatia, Article 9 of the Constitution was amended to allow extradition in cases where a decision on extradition or surrender is executed pursuant to an international agreement or EU law.¹⁷ This provision was introduced prior to EU accession to secure extradition both with EU member states and with non-EU countries. In this regard, it is worth noting that Croatia has also concluded extradition agreements with regional states, including North Macedonia. Notably, the provision regarding surrender pursuant to EU law was postponed until Croatia’s accession to the EU.¹⁸

In summary, some countries (Latvia, Lithuania, Romania, Bulgaria) adopted constitutional formulations allowing extradition of nationals pursuant to ratified

¹³ Article 98, second sentence of the Latvian Constitution provides that: “A citizen of Latvia may not be extradited to a foreign country, except in the cases provided for in international agreements ratified by the *Saeima*, if by the extradition the basic human rights specified in the Constitution are not violated.”

¹⁴ Article 13 of the Lithuanian Constitution prescribes that: “It shall be prohibited to extradite a citizen of the Republic of Lithuania to another state unless an international agreement to which the Republic of Lithuania is a party establishes otherwise.”

¹⁵ Article 19 of the Romanian Constitution prescribes that: “(1) No Romanian citizen shall be extradited or expelled from Romania. (2) By exemption to the provisions of paragraph (1), Romanian citizens can be extradited based on international agreements to which Romania is a party, according to the law and on a mutual basis.”

¹⁶ Article 25, paragraph 4 of the Bulgarian Constitution prescribes that: “(4) (amend., SG 18/05) No Bulgarian citizen may be surrendered to another state or to an international tribunal for the purposes of criminal prosecution, unless the opposite is provided for by an international treaty that has been ratified, published and entered into force for the Republic of Bulgaria.”

¹⁷ Article 9, paragraph 2 of the Croatian Constitution provides that “A citizen of the Republic of Croatia may not be forcibly expelled from the Republic of Croatia nor deprived of citizenship, nor extradited to another state, except in the execution of a decision on extradition or surrender made in accordance with an international treaty or the *acquis communautaire* of the European Union.”

¹⁸ Article 152 of the Constitution of Croatia (consolidated text)

international agreement. Slovenia stands out as a particular case, restricting extradition solely to EU member states. Other countries, such as Poland and Croatia, provide dual options: extradition pursuant to international agreements and EU law.

Constitutional conflicts related to the EAW did arise, with cases before the Polish, German, Cypriot, Czech and Belgian Constitutional courts. The Belgian court, using the preliminary reference procedure, referred the matter to the European Court of Justice in 2005. Although this case did not definitely resolve the EAW saga, the instrument was not ultimately endangered. National constitutional courts played an “active role as judicial interlocutors,” finding “creative” ways to avoid breaching EU law, including granting national legislators time to adopt necessary legislative amendments (Sarmiento, 2008).

CONSTITUTIONAL RESOLUTIONS IN NORTH MACEDONIA FOR ENSURING EFFECTIVENESS OF THE EUROPEAN ARREST WARRANT

With the aim of strengthening regional cooperation among the Balkan countries, the Republic of North Macedonia joined the circle of states that allow extradition of domestic nationals under certain conditions. Amendment XXXII, adopted in April 2011, amended Article 4, paragraph 2 of the Constitution to provide that:

“A citizen of the Republic of Macedonia cannot be deprived of citizenship, nor can he/she be expelled from the Republic of Macedonia. A citizen of the Republic of Macedonia cannot be extradited to another country, except based on a ratified international agreement upon a decision of the Court.”

When compared with similar provisions in the constitutions of the Eastern European EU member states, it is clear that the Constitution of North Macedonia complies with the EU *acquis*’ requirement that extradition be based on a judicial decision. In this regard, it should be noted that Poland constitutionally conditions extradition upon a judicial decision, whereas other countries regulate this issue by law. Estonia is the only country whose Constitution provides that “Extraditions are decided by the Government of the Republic”¹⁹ – a provision that has been criticized and for which interventions have been demanded.

Interpreting the constitutional provision in North Macedonia, one may conclude that it complies with EU *acquis* criteria. Specifically, execution of the EAW derives from a framework decision of the EU, or secondary legislation, the implementation of which is an obligation under accession treaties.

It is worth noting that during the public debate preceding the adoption of Amendment XXXII, there were proposals to allow extradition only to international courts (Government of the Republic of Macedonia, 2011). In the context of EU integration process, such a proposal would have excluded the national courts of EU member states, which are the only authorities empowered to issue EAWs, and would have contradicted the purpose of the amendment. At the time of adoption, bilateral agreements were being concluded in the Balkans with the aim, among others, of enabling extradition of domestic nationals. Consequently, countries first amended their constitutions. North Macedonia played an active role in regional cooperation and the fight against crime, adopting the amendment and subsequently concluding agreements on cooperation in criminal matters –including extradition – with Croatia, Serbia and Montenegro.

¹⁹Article 36, paragraph 2 of the Constitution of Estonia.

CONCLUSION

The constitutional provision in North Macedonia currently complies with EU *acquis* criteria. This conclusion follows from the fact that extradition is permitted on the basis of an international agreement ratified in accordance with the Constitution. In this regard, it must be taken into consideration that accession treaties are, in fact, international agreements that North Macedonia will conclude with the European Union and its member states, and these treaties must be ratified by the national Parliament in order to enter into force. Moreover, accession treaties will oblige North Macedonia to fully implement the EU *acquis* from the first day of accession. Therefore, through deduction as a method of legal interpretation, full implementation of the EAW can be secured.

Nevertheless, to avoid practical difficulties and delays in interpretation by legal practitioners, it would be useful to supplement the constitutional provision. Suggested options include either explicitly recalling EU law as a legal basis for allowing extradition of domestic nationals or directly referencing possible extradition to EU member states. The choice would depend on the context of negotiations and the readiness of Macedonian legal practitioners to apply EU law on a daily basis.

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